

HIGH SPECTRAL AND TEMPORAL RESOLUTION IMAGING ANALYSIS FOR MONITORING ALGAL BLOOM IN WATER RESERVOIR IN THE WARM SEASON

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ABSTRACT

Extensive eutrophication process in water body may lead to the creation of algal blooms, reduction in oxygen supplies, death of aquatic life and danger to human health. Monitoring eutrophic processes is therefore mandatory to the aquatic environment and human health. However, the changes in the spatial and seasonal distribution of the phenomena are difficult to be resolved using sparse water sampling or acquisition of remote sensing data. Therefore, this research work proposes a methodology that takes advantage of the temporal and spectral resolution of Sentinel-2 (S2) for monitoring eutrophic reservoir. Specifically, it uses large temporal series of S2 images and advanced temporal unmixing model to study the spectral response of the turbid and productive water of San Roque reservoir, Argentina. The spatial patterns and the temporal tendencies of these aquatic indicators are analysed and evaluated in order to assess their contribution to the local water management.

Index Terms— Eutrophication, phytoplankton, Sentinel-2, multitemporal, unmixing, turbid water

1. INTRODUCTION

Eutrophication is the process in which the primary production of a water body increases with the contribution of organic matter and nutrients. As consequences, these waters are characterised with high production of biomass at all trophic levels and large quantitative and qualitative changes in the phytoplankton community that may lead to algae blooms [1]. In order to assess the quality of water bodies, quantitative indicators are required to describe the frequency and the intensity of the blooms. Chlorophyll-a concentration [Chl-a] is widely used as an indicator of biomass and to characterize the trophic state of water body [2]. In the case of San Roque Reservoir, Córdoba, Argentina large amounts of nutrients, nitrogen and phosphorous species, lead to massive development of algae during summer. As this water body is the most important source of water supply in the Province, the detection of

blooms events is extremely important. Algal blooms are monitored in the lake solely by *in situ* measurements. However, during blooms events when the spatial distribution of phytoplankton biomass is high, conventional water sampling is not sufficient to characterize the distribution of the algae [3]. In this framework, remote sensing becomes an essential and effective monitoring tool of algal bloom. In the passed decades, Landsat and MODIS program had been successfully used to monitor [Chl-a] in San Roque reservoir [4, 5, 6]. However, their lower spatial resolution or sparse acquisition disabled the joint extraction of spatial patterns and temporal trends. Sentinel-2 provides higher spatial, temporal and spectral resolutions in comparison to precedent Earth Observation (EO) programs [7, 8]. The assumption is therefore that if temporal-spectral patterns are taken into account, the extraction of eutrophic indicators will improve accordingly. Recently, temporal spectral unmixing methods have been successfully applied to several applications [9] including water monitoring [10]. In this work, we advance the research by analysing and validating a multitemporal unmixing approach to eutrophication processes.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Field data

Field data used in this work was collected and generated in the context of a monitoring program carried out by the local government of the province of Córdoba, Argentina [11, 3]. San Roque reservoir is located in Villa Carlos Paz city in Córdoba province, Argentina (31° 22' 56" S, 64° 27' 56" W) at 643 meters above sea level.

For this research work, water samples were collected in eight measurement stations located in the reservoir (Figure 1). Specifically, 11 water samples were collected simultaneously with Sentinel-2 passes during the summer seasons on the 26/01/2016 and the 22/02/2017 and 14 samples were collected during the spring season on the 14/11/2018 and 21/11/2017. Secchi Disk Depth measurements were performed *in situ* according to SMWW-Met 2130-B method [12], while Suspended Solids, [Chl-a], Turbidity and Total

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Fig. 1. Locations of sampling stations (in pink) superimposed on Sentinel-2A image of San Roque reservoir from the 22nd February 2017.

Algae measurements were performed at the laboratory by SMWW-Met 2540 D, SMWW-Met 10200 H.2.b., SMWW-Met 130 B and SMWW-Met 10200 F methods, respectively [12]. A summary of the field data measurements are presented in Table 1 and Table 2.

2.2. Satellite data

From 2016 till 2019, 37 and 26 Sentinel-2 (A and B) images were acquired during the summer and spring seasons, respectively. These images were automatically downloaded using the module *i.sentinel.download* available on GRASS GIS [13]. The images that contain less than 30% clouds cover, were atmospherically corrected using the dedicated package Sen2cor [14] available as a standalone version. Finally, the water area of interest was cropped and masked.

2.3. Unmixing models

The selected unmixing model is based on linear mixing assumption and is conducted in three stages. In the first stage, the HySime (Hyperspectral signal subspace estimation) [15] is used to determine the number of endmembers present in the image. In the second stage, we used the open source algorithm 'Online unmixing of multitemporal hyperspectral

Table 1. Summary of chemical field measurements

[Chl-a] mg/m ³	Secchi Disk (m)
Summer mean (range)	
192.2 (27.60 - 881.00)	0.71 (0.30 - 1.00)
Spring mean (range)	
156.19 (4.57 - 703.12)	0.91 (0.25 - 1.40)
Suspended Solids (mg/L)	Turbidity (NTU)
Summer mean (range)	
29.75 (6.00-79.00)	20.60 (8.50 - 44.00)
Spring mean (range)	
16.38 (1.00 - 53.00)	9.60 (2.90 - 42.70)

Table 2. Summary of biological field measurements (Org/L)

Total Algae	Dynophyta	Cyanophyta
Summer mean (range)		
2469643 (670000 - 7600000)	744900 (9600 - 1500000)	850950 (3800 - 2600000)
Spring mean (range)		
1682477 (431640 - 4303600)	666667 (400000 - 1200000)	571500 (14000 - 1300000)

images' proposed by [16] to identify the multitemporal endmembers from the long series of the S2 images. Finally, the fully constraint least squares linear spectral unmixing (FCLSU) [17] is used to calculate the abundances of each endmember. This algorithm minimizes the square error in the linear approximation of the image by imposing nonnegative and sum-to-one constraints for the abundances [18]. For comparison purposes we applied the vertex component analysis algorithm (VCA) proposed in [19], on single images from the 22/02/2017 and the 26/01/2016. The retrieved abundances using the multitemporal and the simple mixing models were evaluated, compared and discussed.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Temporal Unmixing

The temporal unmixing model resulted in the extraction of three endmembers for each season (Figure 2). The thick red line presents the seasonal spectra and the dashed blue line its contributing (dMt) vectors. As expected in turbid water, the spectra contain the absorption features of water as well as the optical properties of organic and inorganic materials. The spectra of the turbid water, Endmember-1 in Figure 2 are characterised by high reflectance along the VNIR wavelengths (490-740 nm; bands 2 to 6 of S2). Endmember-2 presents a typical Chl-a spectra with high reflection in the red

Fig. 2. Multitemporal endmembers extracted using long series of S2 images; in thick red line the seasonal spring endmember and in dashed blue line its perturbant (dMt) vectors.

wavelengths (664–782 nm; bands 4 to 7 of S2) and secondary small reflectance peak of the green pigment (i.e. photosynthesis process by the algae) at 550–665 nm (bands 2 to 4 of S2). These observations are supported by the *in situ* measurements which found very high number of green algae, phylum Cyanophyta (Table 2), that were flooded to the reservoir through the dam.

The temporal spectra of Endmember-3 show additional reflectance peak in bands 8A (865 nm) to the high reflectance in the MWIR wavelengths (bands 2 to 7 of S2). This peak is probably due to the presence of *Ceratium hirundinella* (brown/red algae) in the lake. The two algae groups, Cyanophyta and Dynophyta *Ceratium* are frequently predominant in the reservoir.

Nevertheless, the spectra of Endmember-3 show high reflectance in the SWIR wavelengths (band 12 of S2). This feature could be due to the contribution of sediments to the lake from nearest tributaries, given that the spring and the summer are the rainy seasons and income water is loaded with organic matter. The reflectance values in these wavelengths are specially high in the spring when the load of sediments from the nearest rivers is massive [20].

3.2. Validation using Regression Model

For validation, we calculated the correlations of the variables measured in the field and the abundances calculated using the three temporal endmembers for the selected summer and the spring dates. Specifically, Pearson correlations were calculated between the abundance pixels at the sampling locations and the measured [Chl-a], Turbidity, Secchi Disk, Suspended Solids and Total Algae. For the summer, the result for the correlation between [Chl-a] and the abundances ratio calculated for Endmember-2 over Endmember-1, is significant ($R=0.75$, $p=0.013$). These results are consistent with other studies that use empirical model in productive waters [21].

For comparison, the same analysis was made with the abundances calculated using the unmixing of the classical linear unmixing model (VCA), for each date separately. In this case, a poor fit of 0.17 and p-value of 0.75 were found between [Chl-a] and the ratio of the three abundances.

In addition, in the spring we found a significant correlation between Endmember-1 and suspended solids ($R=0.58$, $p=0.018$) as well as strong significant negative correlation with Secchi disk ($R=(-0.79)$, $p=0.0008$). As the concentration of suspended solid and algae are high in the lake the transparency of the water (which is measured using the Secchi disk) is reduced. From the field data, we found negative significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation between Secchi disk and

turbidity ($R=(-0.80)$) and also with suspended solids ($R=(-0.91)$). At the same time, turbidity and suspended solids obtained significant ($p < 0.05$) and high correlation of $R=0.95$ and $R=0.77$, respectively with total algae. We therefore assume that the transparency of the water is affected by the high load of organic and inorganic matters in the reservoir.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This scientific work highlights the significance of temporal-spectral analysis of turbid water in comparison to the analysis using a single EO acquisition. The dynamic of turbid water results in large daily spectral variation that diminished the efficiency of water quality models that are based on satellite data. Nevertheless, the results also show that temporal-spectral analysis can better resolve seasonal spectral pattern and help in understanding the temporal inter-variation of algae within the reservoir.

Although the high temporal and spectral characteristics of Sentinel-2, the extraction and separation of water retrievals using spectral analysis remain challenge in turbid water. As mentioned by [7] [22] [23], the high mixing rate in the water prevents the spectral unmixing of Chl-a and algae species from other optically active compounds like suspended sediment and colored dissolved organic matter.

Further work on temporal algorithms strongly supported by field data collection is required for further validating the capacity of Sentinel 2 to extract and monitor water quality retrievals in inland and turbid water bodies.

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